

SEMANTIC PERCEPTION OF CREOLIZED TEXT

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***Annotation:** In this article, basically, the theory is important, an attempt has been made to show the results of experimental studies. The information posted here can be viewed in two ways, on the one hand, these are experimentally approved rules, on the other hand, some of them they still have a hypothetical character, naturally, only still waiting for verification in the experiment.*

***Key words:** theory, rule, research, methodology, expression, text, problem, semantics, concept.*

To solve the problem of semantic perception of a creolized text (CT), theoretical knowledge (scientific categories) is of paramount importance, which allows us to most adequately describe not only the processes of understanding CT, but also the explanation of the real reality that is displayed (modeled by verbal and nonverbal signs) using CT.

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We begin our presentation with an analysis of the assumptions within which it is possible to solve the problem of semantic perception of CT.

A.N. Leontiev gave an adequate psychological definition of activity for our purposes: “it is a unit of life mediated by mental reflection, the real function of which is that it orients the subject in the objective world” [Leontiev 2012: 62]. From this definition it follows that human activity is an instrument of cognition of the objective world, which (the instrument) gives cognized objects not only objective qualities; independent of the subjective positions of a person as a researcher. The fact is that the needs of a person, prompting his activity to master objects that satisfy these needs, give it an appropriate meaning, because all actions that make up the activity are subordinated to the need to achieve these objects. In other words, activity as an instrument of cognition gives cognized objects not only objective meaning, but also subjective meaning.

The second assumption is expressed by the statement that communicants who communicate using signs must have a community of their consciousnesses, which is created as a result of mastering their (common to them) ethnic culture, which becomes the property of their consciousness in the form of images of consciousness during interiorization.

In the cultural-historical school of L.S. Vygotsky, the position is substantiated, according to which the consciousness of a child is formed in the process of his cooperation with an adult, when the social relations of a child and an adult become a fact of the child's consciousness: "We can formulate a general genetic law of cultural development in the following form: every function in the cultural development of a child appears on the stage twice, in two plans, first – social, then psychological, first between people, as an interpsychic category, then within the child, as an intrapsychic category" [Vygotsky 1984: 145].

In accordance with the principle of objectivity of A.N. Leontiev's activity [Leontiev 2012: 69], perception and, consequently, the construction of perception images are attributed to objects of real reality, i.e. the image of perception is formed in the external environment "on the object" for the purpose of identifying it, and only after the formation of this external image it is internalized. The process of perception itself splits into the stage of sensory perception and the stage of perceptual perception (the stage of perceptual actions for processing sensory data).

When analyzing the stage of sensory perception, the task of identifying an object is distinguished using a set of allocated sensory data that provides identification. After that, the totality of the selected sensory data (also called "sensory mass", "sensory response", "sensory image") is compared with the sensory reference.

The sensory standard as a set of signs of previously perceived similar objects is formed from the practical needs of the activity in which perception unfolds as an indicative activity: during the Great Patriotic War, Soviet pilots were supplied with albums with silhouettes of enemy aircraft.

The result of perceptual processing of sensory data is an image of perception of a particular object after it is identified with images of memories of similar objects, i.e. images acting as a perceptual standard, if, naturally, such an image is present in the observer's mind. Consequently, the subject of perception can identify only the object for which he has perceptual standards.

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Otherwise, this identification will be accompanied by various limitations that make the results of perception approximate. Now we proceed to the presentation of ideas about the process of semantic perception of CT, some of these ideas are still hypothetical and are waiting, as we have already mentioned, for experimental verification.

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